

Halide-Alkoxides of Iron(III)

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Chloride and bromide derivatives of ferric alkoxides have been prepared by the reactions of acetyl chloride and bromide respectively. Reactions of isopropyl and *tert*-butyl acetates on ferric chloride and of hydrogen chloride on ferric isopropoxide have also been studied. Radical interchange reactions between ferric chloride and alkoxides have been demonstrated.

The preparation and properties of ferric alkoxides have been studied by a number of workers¹⁻³. A survey of the literature revealed that no attempt has so far been made for the preparation of halide alkoxides of iron (III). A number of halide alkoxides of various elements⁴⁻²⁰ have been prepared, in recent years, in these laboratories.

In the present investigations the reactions of acetyl halides (acetyl chloride and bromide) have been carried out with ferric alkoxides. In the case of ferric isopropoxide the reactions were found to be facile, and can be represented by the following equations:

(where X = Cl or Br)

Similar to the behaviour of other metal *tert*. butoxides, the reactions of acyl halides with ferric *tert*. butoxide were found to be slow:

(where X = Cl or Br)

1. Thiessen and Koberner, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1929, 180, 65.
2. Mieserwein and Bersin, *Annalen*, 1929, 476, 113.
3. Bradley, Multanj and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 126.
4. Bradley, El. Hakim, Mehrotra and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4609.

Further, the products appear to react with the tert-butyl acetate formed in the reactions to give acetate derivatives. This was further confirmed by the reaction of anhydrous ferric chloride itself with tert.-butyl acetate.

A plausible mechanism for these types of reactions has already been suggested by Mehrotra and Misra^{5,6}.

The replacement of the alkoxide group by the more electronegative halide group appears to decrease the electron density round the iron atom and thus increase its capacity for acceptance of donor bonds from organic esters. This fact was further supported by the following reaction of isopropyl acetate with ferric chloride:

Ferric chloride alcoholate having two moles of isopropanol was obtained when a stream of dry hydrogen chloride was passed through a solution of ferric isopropoxide in benzene.

A facile quantitative radical interchange has been shown to take place between ferric chloride and alkoxides as shown below:

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Anhydrous ferric chloride (B.D.H.) was sublimed in an atmosphere of chlorine before use. Alcohols and benzene were dried and purified as described^{5,6}. Ferric isopropoxide^{7,8} (b.p., 149-155° C/0.1 mm.) was prepared by the action of sodium isopropoxide on ferric chloride. Ferric tart. butoxide (subliming at 135-146°C/0.1 mm.) was prepared by alcoholysis.

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15. Gupta and Mehrotra, *this Journal* (in Press).
16. Misra, *Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University*, 1963.
17. Misra, *Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University*, 1964.

TABLE I

Reactions of $Fe(OPr)_3$ with CH_3COX

No	Reactants in 'g' & molar ratio 'r'		Nature of product	Analysis Found					Analysis Required		
				Fe%	%	Isopropoxy	Fe	OPr/Fe	Fe	%	Isopropoxy
1.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COCl C_6H_6 r=1	(2.48) (0.83) (30.0)	$FeCl(OPr)_2 \cdot 0.5(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Light brown solid insoluble in benzene. (2.73g.).	21.62	13.45	46.29	0.98	2.02	21.43	13.60	45.37
2.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COCl C_6H_6 r=2	(2.82) (1.90) (25.0)	$FeCl_2(OPr)_2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown pasty solid insoluble in benzene (3.41g.).	19.61	24.24	21.20	1.95	1.0	19.39	24.61	21.00
3.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COCl C_6H_6 r=3	(2.02) (2.04) (34.0)	$FeCl_3 \cdot 2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (3.18g.).	15.12	28.61	—	2.98	—	15.24	29.02	—
4.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COCl C_6H_6 r=5	(1.04) (1.75) (40.0)	$FeCl_3 \cdot 2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (1.59g.).	15.49	29.44	—	2.91	—	15.24	29.02	—
5.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COBr C_6H_6 r=1	(1.83) (0.96) (19.0)	$FeBr(OPr)_2$ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.94g.).	22.08	31.54	46.27	0.99	1.98	21.99	31.47	46.56
6.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COBr C_6H_6 r=2	(1.81) (1.91) (25.0)	$FeBr_2(OPr)_2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown pasty solid insoluble in benzene (2.92g.).	14.99	42.35	15.29	1.97	0.96	14.82	42.4	15.69
7.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COBr C_6H_6 r=3	(1.44) (2.29) (15.0)	$FeBr_3 \cdot 2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (3.06g.).	11.26	47.63	—	2.95	—	11.18	47.96	—
8.	$Fe(OPr)_3$ CH_3COBr C_6H_6 r=5	(0.78) (2.06) (20.0)	$FeBr_3 \cdot 2(CH_3COOC_3H_7)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (1.65g.).	10.90	48.19	—	3.09	—	11.18	47.96	—

* [X=Cl or Br.]

TABLE II

No. Reactants in 'g' & molar ratio	Nature of the product	Analysis Found				Analysis Required		
		Fe%	Cl% or Br%	Cl/Fe or Br/Fe	Alk. Eq.	Fe%	Cl% or Br%	Alk. Eq.
1. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.11) CH_3COCl (0.31) C_6H_6 (20.0) $x=1$	$\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_2\text{Cl}$ Light brown solid slightly soluble in benzene (0.95g.).	23.61	14.82	0.98	0.988	23.52	14.93	1.0
2. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.90) CH_3COCl (1.08) C_6H_6 (15.0) $x=2$	$\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)\text{Cl}_{1.5}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_{0.5}$ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.46g.).	26.51	25.01	1.48	1.999	26.39	25.14	2.0
3. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (0.82) CH_3COCl (0.70) C_6H_6 (12.0) $x=3$	$\text{FeCl}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}-)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (0.55).	30.11	38.25	2.00	2.95	30.07	38.18	3.0
4. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.84) CH_3COCl (2.62) C_6H_6 (20.0) $x=5$	$\text{FeCl}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}-)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (1.24g.).	30.21	38.32	1.99	2.98	30.07	38.18	3.0
5. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.41) CH_3COBr (0.63) C_6H_6 (18.0) $x=1$	$\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_2\text{Br}$ Reddish brown solid slightly soluble in benzene (1.43g.).	19.89	28.10	0.98	0.993	19.81	28.34	1.0
6. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (2.26) CH_3COBr (2.02) C_6H_6 (15.0) $x=2$	$\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)\text{Br}_{1.5}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_{0.25}$ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (2.27g.).	20.18	43.28	1.49	1.960	20.06	43.07	2.0
7. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.59) CH_3COBr (2.14) C_6H_6 (15.0) $x=3$	$\text{FeBr}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}-)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (1.59g.).	20.47	57.98	1.98	2.930	20.33	58.19	3.0
8. $\text{Fe}(\text{OBU}^t)_3$ (1.20) CH_3COBr (2.69) C_6H_6 (18.0) $x=5$	$\text{FeBr}_2(\text{CH}_3\text{COO}-)$ Brown viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (1.16g.).	20.40	58.31	1.99	2.970	20.33	58.19	3.0

Analytical Method.—Iron was estimated gravimetrically as ferric oxide. The number of acid (acetoxy + chloride) groups attached per iron atom was estimated by alkalimetric titration (after filtering ferric hydroxide) with hydrochloric acid. Isopropoxy contents were ascertained by the oxidimetric method²¹ and a correction for ferric was applied.

Reaction between ferric isopropoxide and acetyl chloride in the presence of benzene (Molar ratio 1:1):

The exothermic reaction mixture of acetyl chloride (0.83 g.) and ferric isopropoxide (2.48 g.) in benzene (30 g.) allowed to reflux at 90–106°C for about one and a half hours when

18. Kapoor, Ph.D. Thesis, Rajasthan University, 1965.

19. Mathur and Mehrotra (Private Communication).

20. Arora and Mehrotra (Private Communication).

21. Brady, El-Halim, and Wardlaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

TABLE III

No.	Reactants in 'g'	Molar ratio	Conditions of the experiment	Nature of the product	Analysis Found			Analysis Required						
					Fe%	Cl%	Isopropoxy % or Alk. Eq.	i) Cl/Fe or ii) OP ₁ /Fe	Fe%	C%	Isopropoxy or Alk. Eq.	Fe%	C%	Isopropoxy or Alk. Eq.
1					6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
*1.	FeCl ₃ (0.6485) C ₆ H ₆ (40.0) Fe (OPr) ₃ (1.8640)	1:2	Refluxed 90-100°/4 hrs	Fe Cl (OPr) ₃ Light brown solid in- soluble in benzene (2.488g.).	25.60	16.91	55.82	(i) 0.9837 (ii) 1.85	25.66	16.96	56.41			
*2.	FeCl ₃ (2.4430) C ₆ H ₆ (29.0) Fe (OPr) ₃ (1.7560)	2:1	Refluxed 90-95°/2 hrs.	Fe Cl ₂ (OPr) ₂ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (4.032g.).	30.12	37.98	31.52	(i) 1.986 (ii) 0.968	30.06	38.16	31.81			
*3.	Fe Cl ₃ (0.3391) C ₆ H ₆ (20.0) Fe (OBut) ₃ (1.1506)	1:2	Refluxed 90-100°/2 hrs.	Fe Cl (OBut) ₃ Light-brown solid slightly soluble inben- zene (1.4803).	23.6	14.73	—	(i) 0.983	23.52	14.93	—			
*4.	Fe Cl ₃ (0.9078) C ₆ H ₆ (25.0) Fe (OBut) ₃ (0.7700)	2:1	Refluxed 90-100°/3 hrs.	Fe Cl ₂ (OBut) ₂ Brown solid insoluble in benzene (1.677)	28.04	35.13	—	(i) 1.973	27.05	35.48	—			
5.	Fe Cl ₃ (2.01) C ₆ H ₆ (16.0) Isopropyl- acetate (6.97)	1:5	Refluxed 90-100°/2 hrs.	Fe Cl ₂ .2(PiOAc) Viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (4.5g)	15.49	29.44	—	(i) 2.99	15.24	29.02	—			
6.	Fe Cl ₃ (2.2134) Tert. butyl- acetate (8.30) C ₆ H ₆ (15.0)	1:5	Refluxed 110-115°/24 hrs.	Fe Cl (OAc) (But OAc) Viscous comp. insoluble in benzene (4.1g.).	18.53	23.45	Alk. Eq. 2.94	(i) 1.99	18.45	23.42	Alk. Eq. 3.0			
7.	Fe (OPr) ₃ (1.75) C ₆ H ₆ (30.0) HCl gas in excess	1: excess	Packed at room temp. for 6 hrs.	Fe Cl ₃ , 2PrOH Brown solid (2.11g.).	19.93	37.82	Isopropoxy 42.38	(i) 2.98 (ii) 1.97	19.78	37.66	Isopropoxy 42.58			

* Could not be volatilised.

a brown solid was separated. The volatile substances were removed under reduced pressure and a brown solid (2.73 g.) was obtained. This compound could not be volatilised. Found : Fe, 21.62; Cl, 13.45; OC_2H_5 , 46.29. Calc. for $\text{FeCl}(\text{OPr}^i)_2 \cdot 0.5\text{CH}_3\text{COOPr}^i$: Fe, 21.43; Cl, 13.60; OC_2H_5 , 45.37.

For brevity, details of these reactions are listed in Tables I to V. All the reactions were carried out in dry benzene and were found to be exothermic. None of these derivatives could be volatilised even under very low pressures and the products were found to be insoluble in benzene. The compounds were brown solids and some of them were sticky in nature.

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